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EVIL – A HEURISTIC FOR ENGINEERING ETHICS EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

In engineering ethics education, there is a range of decision-making models that help students, future engineers, to make comprehensive analyses of ethical dilemmas. In addition to decision-making models, heuristics can serve a purpose for simplifying and speeding up the analysis of ethical issues. In this short paper, I introduce the EVIL heuristic, which I developed in a textbook. The basis of the heuristic is Albert Hirschmann's three concepts of Exit, Voice, and Loyalty, complemented with the concept of Insubordination. It can be used in situations where an engineer faces wrongdoing by the organization, and where the only options seem to be to either "stay or go". I discuss this heuristic's benefits and drawbacks for engineering ethics education.

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1 INTRODUCTION

In engineering ethics education, there is a range of decision-making models that help students, future engineers, to navigate ethical dilemmas [2, 7, 10]. van de Poel & Royakkers' ethical cycle [10], Collste's decision-making model [2], and Lennerfors' synthetic model [7], all provide a step by step, often recursive approach, from problem formulations, to an ethical analysis, to action and reflection. They are all designed for ethical issues on both micro and macro level. Maner [11] would probably see these as heuristic models for analysing and solving moral problems, and in his paper he presents a large amount of such frameworks, and synthesises them into a 12-step heuristic model. Although such models are beneficial to moral reasoning and analysis, engineering ethics teaching can also benefit from some simpler heuristics.

Gigerenzer and Gaissmaier [4] define heuristics as “a strategy that ignores part of the information, with the goal of making decisions more quickly, frugally, and/or accurately than more complex methods.” While Gigerenzer and Gassmaier see the benefits of heuristics, showing that they can be as effective as more complex forms of decision making, heuristics can also be seen as conducive to biased decisions [6]. Shah & Oppenheimer (cited in [4]) propose that one of the following ways of effort reduction is operative in all heuristics: (a) examining fewer cues, (b) reducing the effort of retrieving cue values, (c) simplifying the weighting of cues, (d) integrating less information, and (e) examining fewer alternatives.

In this paper, I do not study how people use heuristics, but rather introduce the EVIL (Exit, Voice, Insubordination, Loyalty) heuristic, which I developed in a textbook ([anon]). In my teaching practice, I have used variations of this heuristic to give a common problem: “what would you do if the organization you are working in is engaged in some unethical wrongdoing?” Some students would then say that they would quit their job, since they cannot keep working in a company that does that kind of wrongdoing. Some other students on the other side of the debate state that they need a job, so they would stay in the company. EVIL is a way to quickly devise some more granular strategies of action, at least in introductory sessions of engineering ethics. EVIL is a heuristic in the sense that it reduces alternative actions into four possible actions (type e in Shah & Oppenheimer, cited in [4]). However, it increases the complexity from the simplistic “should I stay or should I go?” to four alternatives. In that sense it is a mid-range heuristic which is used to find a middle ground between a complex decision making (such as the ethical cycle, autonomy matrix, or the synthetic model), and between a dualistic strategy. Through this creation of heuristic, it is possible to induce a new framing of problems for students, scaffolding their learning in engineering ethics.

2 EXIT, VOICE, INSUBORDINATION, LOYALTY

The basis of the heuristic is the three concepts of exit, voice, and loyalty, which were developed by Albert Hirschmann [5] to specify consumers' responses to the deterioration of the quality of goods. In other words, consumers exit (or stop buying the product), they voice their concerns, or they remain loyal and keep buying the product. Hirschmann's concepts have been used in a variety of fields, and introduced to engineering ethics [1, 3], as representing the choice that confronts an engineer when he or she faces wrongdoing by the organization. What this conceptual apparatus does, according to an essay which discusses Hirschmann's work 50 years after it was published, is that it allows us to take on a different perspective on an issue; it is something they "promotes understanding" [9]. Ossandon [9] discusses how Hirschmann combined "exit", which is derived from understandings of market competition, together with "voice" which is more seen as derived from politics, as a resulting from an experience of disappointment.

Boel Berner introduced exit, voice and loyalty into the Swedish engineering ethics literature in 1987 [1], when she discussed how an engineer could behave when facing a dilemma. Both exit and voice were seen as a representation of civil courage, while loyalty was not. Exit, she argues, namely leaving one's company, is perhaps not such a big sacrifice if the market is expanding and if the person is willing to relocate to another company, but in a small town, and for a person who is geographically rooted, it might be a significant sacrifice. Berner gives the example of an engineer who left a weapons producing company and rather took a job as a high school teacher. Voice is seen by Berner as a set of different responses, not just blowing the whistle to media. Rather, she writes that one can refuse to execute immoral orders, that one blows the whistle to union representatives or upper managers, and that one blows the whistle to outside stakeholders, for example the media. Loyalty is basically to follow orders.

I complement this with the concept of *Insubordination*, in other words to go against the organization if one's voice is not heard. In Jenny Chan's work on the harsh management regime at Foxconn, the employees have devised strategies to handle excessive work pressure, when they can not be loyal, nor voice their concerns, nor exit. Chan says:

"The workers and interns are creative. They engage in different tactics of resistance. Sometimes, they just pretend that they are sick and play video games in the dormitory. But of course, they are discovered after one or two days; then they will be brought back to the assembly line. At other times, they deliberately make defective products, which slows down the pace of production." [8]

Similarly, this strategy is evident in popular culture. For example, in the movie *The Incredibles*, where one of the superheroes works in an insurance company. His manager does not want him to let the customer know how they can receive

compensation for harm, in order to maximize profits for the company. The superhero agrees but between the lines he tells exactly how a client should get compensation, by saying: “Listen closely. I'd like to help you but I can't. I'd like to tell you to take a copy of your policy to Norma Wilcox on... Norma Wilcox, W-I-L-C-O-X, on the third floor, but I can't. I also do not advise you to fill out and file a WS2475 form with our legal department on the second floor” and so on [cited in anon].

I can notice through practical experience that students tend to pick up the EVIL heuristic, but I have not investigated its effectiveness for the learning outcomes of engineering ethics education. Anecdotally, in our engineering ethics course, a student wrote in an essay about the application of EVIL to a situation where a civil engineer faced a dilemma, in a war situation, where he was needed as a project manager to build a bridge to transport troops for a surprise ambush. Because of his values of pacifism, he wanted to hinder this project, but he could not do so either through voice or exit (fearing for his life). Rather, he engaged in a strategy where the other project members started to dislike him, and lose confidence in the project. He started to come too late to the meetings, and criticised others' ideas even if they were good, just to slow down the project. Luckily for him, the project was cancelled due to an external reason, but this insubordination was a last resort.

3 CONCLUDING DISCUSSION

This short paper has presented the EVIL heuristic, which is a development of Hirschmann's Exit, Voice, and Loyalty framework. It is a mid-range heuristic in the sense that it is aimed to both specify and reduce the number of options in a critical thinking process, but also to increase the number of options from “should I stay or should I go?” to four options. It could be used in introductory classes in engineering ethics and as a micro-insertion into discussions about dilemmas where an employee perceives wrongdoing in the organization.

But why is the acronym EVIL used rather than another arrangement of the letters E, V, I, and L? EVIL is merely used because it is a word which students tend to remember, and it coheres with how Hirschmann presented his concepts (E,V,L), but there is no priority that comes from the letters being arranged in a certain way. However, from the point of view of students and educators a particular order could be seen as representing a priority. EVIL could then imply that Exit would be a prioritized option when facing moral wrongdoing, followed by voice, insubordination, and loyalty. This predilection for Exit seems ill-founded. Another arrangement that I used before was LIVE, which had a more positive ring to it than EVIL, but then could be taken to imply that Loyalty would be the preferred option (and it led to some confusions about the pronunciation of the word). If a preferred order would have to be established, I would opt for one where Voice is the first option, and Loyalty is the last option, in other words either VEIL or VIEL. Given the heuristic memory effect of EVIL, I have opted for this, but when presenting EVIL to students one could play around with other ways of arranging the letters to explore prioritized kinds of action.

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